

Time Series Forecasting of Active Customers Using Sequence Models: A Comparative Evaluation

Alireza Dehghan

Department of Industrial Engineering
Sharif University of Technology
Tehran, Iran
alirezadehghan@ie.sharif.edu

Moslem Habibi

Department of Industrial Engineering
Sharif University of Technology
Tehran, Iran
mhabibi@sharif.edu

Abstract—Active customer forecasting is crucial for software-as-a-service (SaaS) companies to plan resources and understand customer dynamics. This study benchmarks sequence modeling approaches to predict active customer accounts using a real-world dataset. It evaluates hybrid recurrent and convolutional neural networks against Facebook Prophet models, focusing on both multivariate and univariate time series analysis. Advanced models like Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks and 1D Convolutional Neural Networks (Conv1D) are utilized. A comprehensive preprocessing pipeline and Bayesian hyperparameter optimization ensure robust models. The multivariate LSTM-Conv1D model shows superior performance, with a test mean absolute error of 16.49 and an R-squared of 0.84, outperforming Prophet models and univariate LSTM-Conv1D. The hybrid deep learning architecture excels by incorporating multiple related time series and modeling their complex interactions. The study finds up to a 96.62% improvement in accuracy over the Prophet model, highlighting deep learning's capability to capture intricate customer dynamics. This research provides practical guidelines for effective nonlinear time series modeling in customer forecasting for SaaS companies, enhancing data-driven decision-making.

Keywords—Machine Learning, Neural Networks, Time Series Analysis, Bayesian Optimization, Customer Relationship Management, Customer Experience.

I. INTRODUCTION

The strategic prediction of customer behavior is essential for SaaS companies in effectively managing resources for customer acquisition and retention. By using predictive analytics and machine learning on customer data, this approach enhances forecast accuracy and customer insights. For customer relationship management (CRM) SaaS companies, accurate customer forecasting is especially impactful, helping manage and analyze customer interactions to improve business relationships. Key challenges include predicting future active customers through revenue-driving events like purchases or engagement.

By analyzing data on product usage, support tickets, and customer engagement, CRM SaaS providers can predict renewal rates, upsell opportunities, and churn risk. This allows them to target sales and marketing efforts, tailor product

offerings, and engage at-risk customers. Active forecasting also helps understand the drivers behind trends, guiding product development and strategic decisions.

Effective active customer forecasting requires advanced statistical models and machine learning algorithms to detect complex patterns in CRM data. Neural network architectures often outperform traditional models. Active customers, who actively engage with products and services, are becoming a significant trend across industries, including companies like Pipedrive. These customers participate in creating and delivering value, impacting how businesses engage with them. Customer experience is increasingly important, and understanding active customer behavior is crucial for businesses[1].

Customer activity level is an important metric for companies to track as it provides insights into customer engagement and revenue potential. An “active customer” refers to a customer who has shown recent activity, such as placing an order, opening messages, or logging into their account. Active customers are defined as individuals who have generated transactions or interacted with the product, service, or platform within a specific timeframe. Active customers represent the subset of a company’s total customer base that drives the majority of sales and revenue.

There are various ways companies define and measure active customers based on recency, frequency, and monetary value of transactions. A common definition is a customer who has made a purchase or interacted with the company through any channel within a specified timeframe, often the past 90 days. However, the specific criteria can vary across industries and individual businesses. For example, subscription-based companies may consider active customers to be those with an active subscription, while e-commerce retailers may define activity as one or more orders within a given period.

Time series forecasting, predicting future values based on historical data, is vital for many applications. Techniques like hybrid deep learning models, including LSTM and multi-head attention, address non-linear patterns in data [2, 3]. Accurate performance estimation is crucial for these forecasts. Univariate time series analysis models a single variable over time, extracting patterns to predict future trends [4, 5]. In

contrast, multivariate time series analysis models multiple variables, accounting for their interactions. Advanced models like LSTM and CNNs handle complex multivariate relationships [6, 7].

Neural networks, inspired by the human brain, learn patterns and relationships in data. RNNs process sequential data with an internal state, while LSTMs manage long-term dependencies [8, 9]. Dense layers perform classification, and Conv1D layers learn temporal patterns. Sequence models like RNNs and CNNs are essential for processing sequential data, including time series forecasting [10, 11].

Prophet, an open-source tool by Facebook, models trended and seasonal data using a decomposable approach. It handles trends, seasonality, and holidays, making it robust for irregular time series [12].

Bayesian optimization is an approach to optimize expensive black-box functions by constructing probabilistic models, often using Gaussian processes. It efficiently finds global optima by balancing exploration and exploitation [13, 14].

Accurate forecasting of active customers is vital for CRM SaaS companies, as customer preferences evolve. Advanced forecasting techniques, including neural networks, offer nuanced insights into customer behavior. While traditional methods often fall short, modern sequence models like RNNs and Prophet show promise in customer analytics. This study benchmarks machine learning sequence models for forecasting active customers, aiming to (1) compare deep learning models with simpler alternatives like Prophet, (2) explore univariate versus multivariate approaches, and (3) identify best practices for CRM SaaS analytics. Through experiments on real-world data, we aim to provide valuable insights for practitioners and researchers.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Case Study

This study uses customer data from Didar CRM, a SaaS company providing CRM platforms, to forecast the number of active customers over the next 90 days using time series modeling. The dataset, collected daily from September 26, 2022, to July 21, 2023, includes: 1. Active Accounts: Count of active CRM users, 2. New Accounts: Paid subscription signups, 3. Churned Accounts: Deactivated accounts without renewal, 4. Potential Customers: Volume of potential leads or inquiries, 5. Deals Added: New deals entered in the CRM, 6. Succeeded Deals: Successfully closed deals, 7. Dollar Price: USD to Toman conversion rate.

The objective is to compare sequence model approaches for forecasting active customer numbers for Didar, a cloud-based CRM provider in Iran. Each sale results in a new account, with purchasers enrolling at least one user on the platform. "Deals Added" indicates customer engagement. We aim to model time dependencies in these metrics to forecast future customer numbers accurately.

Didar offers CRM solutions, including contact management, pipeline tracking, task automation, and sales analytics, operating on a SaaS subscription model. Since its founding in 2020, Didar has grown to over 2,000 accounts and 7,500 customers by July 2023. The company experiences sales seasonality and occasional customer churn. Accurate forecasts of active customers and sales metrics are essential for resource planning and revenue projection.

This case study applies both multi and univariate neural network based models, LSTM and Conv1D to the daily customer data. Performance is compared to benchmark Facebook Prophet. The models are implemented in Python using TensorFlow and Keras. Grid Search and Bayesian Optimization method determines optimal model hyperparameters.

B. Data Preprocessing

To ensure reliable analysis, meticulous data preparation was undertaken for time series forecasting. Missing values for new and churned accounts were filled with zeros after generating a complete date range. Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) involves understanding data distributions via histograms and examining relationships using a correlation heatmap. The Pearson correlation coefficient was used to measure these relationships. Time series plots were created to identify trends and seasonal patterns, and seasonal decomposition further broke down the data into observed, trend, seasonal, and residual components.

Outliers in metrics like active accounts and successful deals were detected and treated by setting extreme values to null and interpolating linearly to restore data integrity. Distributions and probability plots were used to validate the outlier treatment. This thorough preparation ensures robust model development and accurate forecasting.

C. Prophet Modeling

The dataset was divided into training and validation sets, where 70% of the data was allocated for training and the remaining 30% for validation. The forecasting model is instantiated using the 'Prophet' class, a popular choice for time series prediction. The Prophet model was first applied to a univariate setup, focusing solely on the "Active Account" metric. The Prophet model was trained on the training set, and predictions were made on the validation set. Mean absolute error (MAE), mean squared error (MSE), and R-squared values were calculated to assess the model's predictive performance.

The modeling scope was then expanded to include additional relevant features: "New Account," "Churned Account," "Potential Customer," "Deal Added," "Succeed Deal," and "Dollar Price." The dataset was split similarly to the univariate case, and the Prophet model was equipped with these features as regressors. The modeling process considered various hyperparameters, including weekly seasonality, Fourier order, mode, and prior scales for the individual features. The final Prophet model, incorporating the optimized hyperparameters, was trained on the training dataset.

Optimized hyperparameters in multivariate model are defined as: `growth`, this parameter indicates the expected growth type of the time series. The value `linear` has been set that specifies linear growth. `seasonality_mode`, determines the approach taken for modeling seasonal components in the time series. The value has been set `multiplicative` that signifies the seasonal effects are multiplicative, meaning they scale with the overall trend. `weekly_seasonality`, this parameter quantifies the strength of the weekly seasonality pattern. A higher value implies a more pronounced weekly effect. The value `14.99438888` is provided, denotes the strength of the weekly pattern in the data. `interval_width`, establishes the width of the prediction intervals for the forecast. The value `0.9` has been set that corresponds to a 90% prediction interval width, signifying that the forecast intervals will encompass 90% of the observed data points.

A distinct aspect of the `Prophet` model is its capability to incorporate custom seasonality components: `add_seasonality` This method introduces a custom seasonal component with a periodicity of approximately 36 time units. The `fourier_order` parameter of `28` determines the flexibility of this seasonality pattern, allowing it to capture intricate variations.

To account for external factors that potentially influence the time series, the `Prophet` model incorporates regressor variables: a regressor named 'New Account' is included in the model. It operates in a multiplicative mode, implying that its impact scales with the underlying trend. The `prior_scale` of `20.16353` modulates the strength of the regression impact. Similarly, a 'Churned Account' regressor is incorporated in a multiplicative mode with a `prior_scale` of `16.36643`. The 'Potential Customer' regressor is integrated into an additive mode, implying an independent additive effect. The `prior_scale` of `16.4274` governs the regularization strength. The 'Deal Added' regressor functions additively, with a `prior_scale` of `81.4576574484`. The 'Succeed Deal' regressor operates additively as well, characterized by a `prior_scale` of `66.520`. The 'Dollar Price' regressor affects the time series multiplicatively with a `prior_scale` of `52.307`. Each regressor variable is carefully chosen to represent external influences on the time series. The selection of multiplicative or additive modes for regressors indicates how their effects interact with the underlying trend and other components of the model. The `prior_scale` parameter modulates the impact strength of the regressors, providing a means of regularization. Moreover predictions were visually juxtaposed with the actual data, using line plots to highlight the predictive power of the model.

D. Neural Networks Modeling

In this phase of the study, advanced neural network architectures were harnessed to delve into the intricate dynamics of the time series data. The data was parsed to extract meaningful temporal information and subsequently scaled using MinMaxScaler to ensure convergence and stability during model training. This step is crucial in maintaining consistent ranges across all variables.

On the other hand feature selection is vital for an optimal model that avoids overfitting and unnecessary complexity. Two distinct strategies were employed to select pertinent features: Random Forest Feature Importance: A RandomForestRegressor was employed to identify the most influential features in predicting the "Active Account" target. The feature importance scores guided the selection of the most relevant metrics. Correlation with Target Variable: Correlation analysis was performed to identify features with high absolute correlation values with the target variable, "Active Account." Additionally, outliers were identified and addressed in the "Active Account" and "Succeed Deal" variables to ensure data integrity and model robustness.

To input the data into the neural network, time series sequences were generated. The training data was divided into sequences of one time step each. The sequences, alongside their corresponding target values, were created to ensure the model's time-dependent learning. The temporal nature of the data was exploited by creating sequential data points for both training and testing. The "createXY" function was developed to generate these sequences, where each point encompassed a one-day span of the chosen variables.

CNN can automatically extract partial features of data by convolutional calculation on original Information. Similarly, Conv1D can convolve one-dimensional signals to identify the underlying rules in sequence data. Conv1D can not only extract more important features from the sequence data, but also reduce the dimension of the sequence. When reduced to length 1, the model can be used for regression modeling [15, 16]. To develop a deeper model in the time series and build an excellent model for Active Account prediction, we propose a hybrid model based on Conv1D and LSTM layers, each tailored to capture the intricate temporal patterns of the data. Dropout layers were also incorporated to mitigate overfitting [17].

TABLE I. UNIVARIATE – MULTIVARIATE SEQUENTIAL MODELS

Layer	Nodes	Characteristics	
Lambda	-	x: tf.expand_dims (x,axis=-1) filters=30, kernel_size=3, strides=1, activation= 'relu', padding= 'causal'	filters=70, kernel_size=7, strides=1, activation= 'relu', padding= 'causal', input_shape= (1, 7)
Bidirectional (LSTM)	60 210	-	-
Bidirectional (LSTM)	32 128	-	-
Bidirectional (LSTM)	16 64	-	-
Dropout Dense	- 8	- 14	0.1 0.01

Dense	1	1	-	-
Compile	-	-	loss=tf.keras.losses.Huber(), optimizer=tf.optimizers.Adam (learning_rate=0.001)	loss=tf.keras.losses.Huber(), optimizer=tf.optimizers.Adam (learning_rate=0.00075)

The models are tuned using Bayesian optimization, focusing on key hyperparameters: Batch size, number of samples processed before updating the network parameters. For a dataset of 209 observations, the univariate model with a batch size of 30 and the multivariate model with 44 results in 7 and 5 iterations per epoch, respectively. Number of epochs, total iterations over the entire dataset, set to 200 for both models. Number of layers, refers to hidden layers in the network. Units per layer, number of neurons in each hidden layer. Input sequence length, number of past observations in each sample, set to 9 for the univariate and 1 for the multivariate model. Dropout, a technique to prevent overfitting by randomly disabling units during training. Objective function (loss function), measures the difference between predicted and actual outputs. The Huber loss, used here, combines squared error for small errors and linear loss for larger errors, making it robust to outliers.

$$L_{\delta}(y, f(x)) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(y - f(x))^2 & \text{for } |y - f(x)| \leq \delta, \\ \delta \times (|y - f(x)| - \frac{1}{2}\delta) & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

Where $f(x)$ is the model prediction and y is the true target value. we found this loss function beneficial for training our LSTM-Conv1D models, as the time series data contained some outliers that traditional MSE loss overly penalized. The Huber loss allowed the model to train more stably and achieve better performance. The default threshold of δ is equal to one.

As mentioned above the neural network architectures were carefully designed to capture temporal dependencies and intricate patterns present in the data. The architectures included: A 1D Convolutional Layer: Applied to extract temporal patterns and relationships. Multiple (three) LSTM Layers: These recurrent layers are adept at capturing long-range dependencies. Dropout Layer: Employed to enhance generalization and reduce overfitting. Dense Layers: Including hidden and output layers for prediction. Also, the "filters" determines the dimensionality of the output space (i.e. the number of output filters in the convolution) and "kernel_size" is an integer or tuple/list of a single integer, specifying the length of the 1D convolution window. Thereafter To capture the non-linearity of the data, a nonlinear function, called activation function, can be applied to the weighted sums of neurons. Rectified linear unit (ReLU) and sigmoid are commonly used activation function.

The neural network's efficacy was rigorously assessed through MSE, MAE, R-squared, and Adjusted R-squared. These metrics provided insights into the model's predictive capabilities and the extent to which it could explain the variance in the observed data.

E. Bayesian Hyperparameter Optimization

Hyperparameters are parameters that are not learned during the training process but are set before the training begins, such as learning rates, batch sizes, and the number of layers in a neural network. Bayesian Hyperparameter Optimization (BHO) is a sophisticated approach that employs Bayesian reasoning as following to intelligently search the hyperparameter space and find the best configuration for a given model.

$$P(M|E) \propto P(E|M)P(M) \quad (2)$$

The above formula reflects the core idea of Bayesian optimization, given evidence data E , the posterior probability $P(M|E)$ of a model M is proportional to the likelihood $P(E|M)$ of overserving E given model M multiplied by the prior probability of $P(M)$ [18]. Bayesian Optimization aims to efficiently explore the hyperparameter space by selecting the most promising points to evaluate the objective function, which measures the performance of the model with specific hyperparameters. It does so by constructing a probabilistic model of the objective function based on the points that have already been evaluated. This model is updated iteratively as new points are evaluated, allowing the optimization process to adapt and refine its exploration strategy.

III. 4. FINDINGS AND RESULTS

A. Data visualization

Initial data visualization and exploratory analysis provided insight into the distribution and temporal patterns of key customer metrics as well as the characteristics and trends of the time series data. Overall time series plot of each metric that displays data points over dates is provided in Figure 1 below:

Fig.1. Scatter plots for all metrics.

Which a huge drop in active accounts before April 2023 for approximately one week is obvious, Also it is evident that there is a sharp increase almost days after May 2023 in deals added and succeed deals.

The histogram plots (Figure 2) revealed that most metrics like new account, churned account, deal added, and succeed deal exhibited left-skewed distributions.

Fig.2. Histograms of all variables.

Histogram analysis showed the active account data was right-skewed, with most days having under 1800 active accounts but a long tail stretching to around 2000 accounts on peak days.

Correlation analysis (Figure 3) found that logically succeed deals had strong positive correlation with deals added (0.84), furthermore potential customers shown relatively high correlation with deals added (0.56), and new accounts (0.53). While dollar price pointed out moderately negative correlation with new accounts (-0.2), it had considerable correlation with active accounts (0.47).

Fig.3. Heatmap of correlation matrix.

On the other hand, there were some meager correlations worth to notice, such as new accounts with active accounts (0.036) and churned accounts (0.082), also potential customers with dollar price (0.095) and churned accounts (0.086). Moreover, seasonal decomposition (Figure 4) uncovered clear monthly and weekly seasonal components underlying the fluctuations in active accounts and other metrics. This demonstrates predictable periodic effects that can be modeled. Besides, Decomposing the active accounts time series highlighted oscillating above and below a steadily rising trend, exactly in opposite of new accounts which has shown a falling trend.

Fig.4. Decomposition of all variables.

The data visualization and exploratory analysis provided a solid foundation for subsequent modeling by highlighting inherent patterns, relationships and potential issues to address in the raw time series dataset. Key insights included seasonality, correlations between metrics, and presence of outliers - all crucial considerations when developing robust predictive models. These findings guided preprocessing decisions and model selections to account for data characteristics. The visual and descriptive analysis ensures an informed approach for the predictive modeling tasks.

B. Models Forecasts

TABLE II. A MARSHALL OF STUDY'S RESULTS

Model	BHO	MAE	MSE	R2	Adj. R2
Univariate Prophet	-	327.36	122250.58	-35.42	-
Multivariate Prophet	✓	93.55	14036.95	-3.18	-3.48
Univariate LSTM-Conv1D	✓	19.12	638.67	0.81	-
Multivariate LSTM-Conv1D (test set)	✓	16.49	474.65	0.84	0.83
Multivariate LSTM-Conv1D (training set)	✓	9.26	174.89	0.98	0.98

The high error and negative R-squared indicates Prophet performs poorly in modeling this univariate active accounts series. The predominantly linear modeling of growth trends and seasonal patterns fails to capture the intricate dynamics in the data. Prophet relies on additive trends and seasons, while the active accounts series likely has more complex nonlinear relationships. The external regressors in Prophet also could not be utilized in this univariate context. The univariate Prophet model's linear assumptions occur in oversimplified modeling. The inability to learn nonlinear temporal effects leads to large errors on the active accounts forecasting task.

Incorporating additional metrics and implementing bayesian hyperparameters optimization significantly enhanced Prophet's predictive accuracy, with the multivariate model achieving an MSE of 14036.95 (88.5% improvement) and MAE of 93.55 (71.4% improvement) on the validation set.

The Prophet model was expanded to a multivariate context by incorporating additional time series as regressor variables.

This included new accounts, churned accounts, potential customers, deals added, succeed deals, and dollar price.

This demonstrates the multivariate LSTM-Conv1D model's ability to effectively learn complex linear and nonlinear relationships between metrics that enhance predictive accuracy. Showing it could closely model the complex spatiotemporal dependencies in the customer data. Also, the gap between training and testing performance indicates some overfitting, though not substantial.

Fig.5. Feature importance.

Feature importance analysis revealed dollar price specifically and then by a notable margin deal added, succeed deals, and potential customer as top predictors. The 1D convolutional layer's automatic feature extraction along with multiple LSTM layers enabled modeling of intricate linear and nonlinear relationships between metrics over time. Table below summarizes the all Sequence Models performances.

The multivariate LSTM-Conv1D model delivered state-of-the-art accuracy and significantly outperformed all previous benchmarks and did best among all approaches, including univariate LSTM-Conv1D and Prophet models, demonstrating the value of exploiting cross-variable relationships through deep learning for enhanced accuracy. The hybrid deep learning architecture learned both linear and non-linear relationships between metrics that improved active account forecasts. The results highlight the benefits of leveraging multiple related time series and modeling their interactions. On top of that bayesian hyperparameter tuning enabled an optimally configured model.

IV. CONCLUSION REMARKS

This study evaluates modern sequence modeling techniques for forecasting active customer accounts in the software-as-a-service (SaaS) domain, highlighting their importance for sales planning and resource allocation. Using a real-world CRM dataset from Didar over 10 months, the research benchmarks advanced machine learning methods against traditional statistical approaches.

The multivariate LSTM-Conv1D model outperformed others by capturing complex nonlinear spatiotemporal dependencies through deep neural networks, incorporating multiple related time series, and achieving the lowest errors and highest explanatory power. In contrast, Facebook Prophet, constrained by linear assumptions, underperformed.

The study demonstrates the advantages of flexible nonlinear modeling tailored to customer data dynamics. Techniques like long short-term memory networks, 1D convolutional layers, and Bayesian hyperparameter optimization effectively extracted features and patterns. These findings support the use of deep learning for accurate customer time series forecasting, aiding data-driven decisions in sales, marketing, pricing, and strategic initiatives for SaaS companies like Didar CRM.

While promising, the research has limitations, such as the need for larger datasets and the exploration of alternative neural network architectures and advanced methods. Future research should focus on these areas to enhance predictive accuracy. Nonetheless, this study significantly contributes to the literature on predictive analytics in customer relationship management.

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

- A. [Link to the Python codes.](#)
- B. [Link to the zip file of all output pictures.](#)

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